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dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

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A Reference Frame for Self-Studies and Self-Regulatory Mechanism of Vedas: Personality Changes

[Swami Parmarth Dev¹, Sadvi Dev Priya²,
Anjali Prabhakar³ and Paran Gowda⁴]⁵

Abstract

Self-study of Vedas and its intrinsic regulatory mechanism leads to many personality changes such as learning vedantic life skills - professional management skills, creativity, competitiveness, responsiveness, adaptability, independence, communication, social engagement, emotional balance, health awareness etc. This process is also a true way to understand the core of personality. Our study is focused on the effect of Self-study of Upanishads and their correlation with the personality aspects. A frame of reference is chosen from eleven Major Upanishads . A time frame of 1 week is required in the assessment process.

Key words

Self studies; Self regulatory mechanism; Vedas and Upanishads;
Frame development; Questionnaire

1. Introduction

In the present day, Indian Vedas and Upanishads , are considered as Hindu religious text books. But scientifically, it is not. Abid mentioned in his studies that Upanishads are an amalgamation of philosophy and mysticism which are general ethical and spiritual methods to reach a

1 Research Scholar, University of Patanjali, Haridwar

2 Dean, Yoga and Philosophical Sciences, University of Patanjali, Haridwar

3 Research Scholar, University of Patanjali, Haridwar

4 Professor, University of Patanjali, Haridwar

5 Authors contribution: The first two authors have contributed to the questionnaire development by culling out from vedic text books. and the remaining co-authors contributed to the data analysis and its interpretation.

state of equanimity and bliss (1). Ipsit Pratap Singh in his study provides a vision about Vedic management through vedic wisdom of Veda and upanishads on the concept of a holistic living which is deeply rooted in Universal compassion and care. Menon *et al.*, explores the self and consciousness through Taittiriya Upanishad. In this direction, many of vedic scholars carried out research and found astonishing results (13). Goparaj and Sharma gave good scientific reasoning in understanding the Vedas and Upanishads. Alpna & Anshu interpreted Vedic mantras in a therapeutic way and its effect on stress, anxiety etc(1). Bansal *et al.*, narrated the use of life skills – empathy, communication, adaptive agility and EI (emotional intelligence) concepts from Bhagavad Gita. However, the above authors have not focused on whether life skills are taught by the gurus or Self Studies by the students. Sayee & Vasuki, in their study found that ancient wisdom in Bhagavad Gita provides professional supervision including psychological well being (4). Manjunath *et al.*, mentions that vedas are inherited from our ancestors through hearing the mantras using the techniques of recitation by words. In the ancient days, the process of learning was through exchange of knowledge, conduct and the right attitude towards life. Binita shows that self study of Upanishads, especially Katha Upanishad, speaks about the moral principles like satya, tyaga, tapas ,dhana etc (3). Suparna et al., states in the research work into the realm of cognition and provides a philosophy, based on the yoga of selfless action, to inform the runner and the course of study. The paper also includes a bit for a curriculum development on selflessness (11). Roopali mentioned in her study about the influence of cultural narratives on the experience of self and the process of re-construction of self in post traumatic growth (7). Sankul et al., in their study, represents the effect of spirituality on Compassion /self compassion among emerging adults (3). Kadek Surpi provides a direction towards the concept of education pattern. Upanishad is an integral part of Vedic literature, and it provides the basic concepts of education and literacy patterns. According to the Upanishads, education is about giving academic degrees to students and building excellent human character; literacy is essential in Hindu Education. Various educational methods are used in the Upanishads, with the aim of awakening all human

potential (9). Naval Garg in his paper, aims to empirically explore the impact of six dimensions of workplace spirituality on three types of organizational commitment. Six dimensions of workplace spirituality used for the study are Swadharma, Lokasangraha, authenticity, sense of community, Karma capital and Krityagyata. Components of organizational commitment are affective, normative (1). Varaprasad and Anupama state that happiness plays an important role in the effective employee engagement (EEE). Vijaylaxmi et al., in his study has shown the role of the value education system through Vedic wisdom.

In the present study, we tried to fill this gap of self –studies and its mechanism of learning by students. In this direction, some researchers have attempted to fill this gap. Kaushal *et al.*, shows the happiness role in human life by considering the ancient Vedic perspective of wisdom and how it is beneficial in a workplace and in life. The Indian philosophical understanding of Self provides an alternative and wider scope of transformation of self from lower nature which identifies with matter to higher nature which identifies with the spirit in Vedas and Upanishads . In the same way we are also presenting the significant changes in the level of happiness (“Diener”) through self study of Vedic scriptures in a scientific way. In the same direction our study also measures the various attributes like happiness, quality of life in a scientific approach among the students who take up the studies of Upanishads leading to happiness , joyful, self-esteemed personality in life and also in physical life. All these terms culminate towards our wholesome personality development. Self study process of Upanishads also leads to significant differences in the level of self – esteem , happiness and quality of life in a scientific and measurable manner in our research. We focused our study on the self study of ancient wisdom and saw their effect on various cognitive skills and methods in a scientific manner.

2. Methodology

A reference frame is designed and developed in the interpretation and formulation of questions based on vedic mantras. With this, a scale is developed for a systematic process that is carried out at different stages of analysis. Following recommendations of DeVellis and

Pasqual, scale development for the present study was accomplished in three stages viz; item generation, theoretical analysis and psychometric analysis.

2.1 Theoretical analysis:

Self Regulatory mechanism in Mantra sciences i.e. Upanishads Vedic Mantras have subtle effects on brain neurons of the physical body. How mantras affect the brain and its self regulatory mechanism is still unexplored science. There are some efforts in this direction by Artificial Intelligence computer programmers (Tanwar 145). It's a separate mantra science by itself. Self studies and recitation of the mantras have subtle effects on the physiology and functioning of the central nervous system (Tanwar 145).

2.2 Item Generation:

Content domain is specified through review of literature related to 11 major Upanishads (for example, Bhagavad Gita) from Indian Philosophy to explain the self-regulatory mechanism of personality changes observed in the students. . Among the teachings of Upanishads, there are 11 major ones that relate with self-studies to specify the content domain. The scale comprises of 26 item domain from (i) Taittiriopanishad: Janki parikha (2017), (ii) Kathopanishad: Swami chinmayananda (2016), (iii) Chandogya: Jibananda vidyasagar (2009), (iv) Mundaka: Swami Gambhirananda (2010), (v) Mandukya : Swami Nikhilananda (2006), (vi) Kena: Maitreyia Gautam (20018), (vii) Aitreya: Manindra Mishra (2017), (viii) Brihadaranyaka: Charles Johnston, (2016), (ix). Ishopanishad: Maharishi Aurobindo (2010) , (x) Svethasvathara: Maheshanandagiri (1975), (xi) Prashnopanishad: Swami Gambhirananda (2010).

The researcher considered all 11 as self-study concepts and formulated 26 questions as the constructs for scale development. Item pool generation provides a conceptual endorsement for the initial item pool. The present research employed combination of deductive and inductive methods of initial item pool generation as recommended by Kapuscinski AN and Masters KS. The researchers also interacted with experts in the field of Indian Philosophy and Yoga sciences and obtained qualitative information regarding the content domains and objective of the research. The information was analyzed and related with

the concept of self-studies with its self-transformation mechanism that are deeply embedded in the teachings of Upanishads by generating it as initial pool items. As a result, 51 items were developed under the selected content domains. Items worded negatively for the construct were reverse coded and scored. Following the recommendations by parameters such simplicity, clarity, specificity, capability to ensure variability of response and freedom from bias of the items were carefully considered while drafting the items.

2.3 Content validity:

Content validity of the initial items was assessed to make sure that the items are representative of the identified construct i.e., Self-studies in Upanishads. The researchers, in order to assess content validity of the initial items, clearly defined the conceptual framework of self-studies in Upanishads by undertaking a thorough literature review and seeking expert opinions. The expert panel comprised of 10 experts; Sanskrit colleges, Delhi, Gurukul Kangdi, Haridwar, one Vedic philosophy expert from Texas, USA, another expert from alternative and complementary medicine, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Rishikesh, statistical expert and a psychology professor Sastra university, yoga expert from University of Patanjali, Haridwar, India. The experts assessed the relevance of items in relation to the content domain applying a tool namely Content Validity Index (CVI) developed by Waltz (p 183). A separate experts scale was provided to evaluate the questions. The experts rated each item against a four-point scale (1=Not relevant, 2= somewhat relevant, 3=Quite relevant and 4=highly relevant). A score of 3 or 4 indicates that the content represented by each item was considered valid and in harmony with the theory that is being measured and they are retained. The items which received score 1 or 2 were rejected from the scale indicates that the theoretically or practically irrelevant questions or any ambiguous items that apparently repeated the essential content of other items.

2.4 Face validity:

Visual appearance of the tool such as consistency of the style, formatting, readability and feasibility as prescribed by Devon HA (pp. 155-164) were tested by applying the initial level scale with 10 individuals. The respondents were asked to judge the user-friendliness

of the tool. Feedback from the respondents was incorporated to improve the tool. This process was helpful to assess ambiguity and skewness i.e., respondents providing very similar answers to all the items.

2.5 Psychometric analysis:

The psychometric analysis involves a number of quantitative techniques to test construct validity and reliability of the scale. Construct validity according to Posakoff PM is the quantity to which interpretation can be meaningfully constructed from the observed scores to the hypothetical constructs about which the observations are meant to hold information. In addition to construct validity, convergent validity, criterion validity and discriminant validity of the scale were tested quantitatively. DeVellis RF strongly recommends the combined use of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to achieve consistent results of the psychometric indices. Hence, these validity tests were done using EFA and CFA. Reliability, a quantification method producing the consistent results on recurring examination, was measured in terms of indicators namely Cronbach Alpha, Spearman-Brown coefficient, composite reliability and average variance extraction. Concurrent validity was assessed by calculating the correlation between the scores of the present scale and an established scale namely Sri Guru Granth Sahib Yoga Scale.

2.6 Data collection and analysis:

In this study the scale was with five options ranging from 'strongly disagree' (score 1) to 'strongly agree' (score 5). Each of the items in the scale is an agreement statement on the five-point Likert scale, which is a quantitative technique meant for measuring psychological variables like attitude, perception, anxiety, stress, beliefs etc. All the items in the scale were positively stated about Sri Guru Granth Sahib Yoga Scale. The summated score of all the items was treated as the quantifiable measure of the construct and it was considered for all quantitative analytical purposes. All items included in the Likert scale were considered as continuous variables. The scale was prepared in English and Hindi to facilitate respondents' comprehension over the statements. The questionnaire was filled by the respondents. Factors

are extracted and a factor structure including the correlation between the factors is proposed by EFA. The proposed factor structure is hypothesized and tested in CFA. If the statistical results fit with the hypothesized model the researcher can conclude that the factor structure is valid. Hence, the study evaluated the scale using both EFA and CFA. IBM SPSS 25 software version was used to calculate descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, and EFA and Cronbach Alpha value. IBM SPSS Amos 25 software version was used to perform CFA. Convergent validity was verified using the Average Variance Extracted, a statistic calculated from values of factor loads. Construct validity was assessed by computing model fitness indices namely p value of Chi square, RMSEA, GFI, AGFI, CFI, TLI, NFI and Chisq/df which were the outputs of confirmatory factor analysis. Discriminant validity was examined by measuring the level of redundancy of items through Modification Indices (MI).

2.7 Theoretical analysis:

The initial item pool consisting of 51 items was vetted by four experts to assess the degree to which the items taken together constitute an adequate operational definition of a constructive content validity. The experts reviewed the initial item pool using a CVI rating tool. CVI was calculated following the recommendation of Waltz (p. 155). The experts gave their rating individually. Then, for each item, the index was calculated as the number of experts giving a rating 3 or 4 and this was divided by total number of experts. The items for which the index was less than 0.75 were considered to be irrelevant eliminated from the original list. From the initial pool, 05 items on the draft SGGS were deemed to be invalid because they yielded CVIs of $1/4=0.25$ to $2/4=0.50$ and were removed with CVI lower than 0.75, All the remaining items were valid with CVIs ranging from 0.75 ($3/4$) to 1 ($4/4$) and were retained which resulted in a 30-item questionnaire. After modifying the scale based on rating by the experts, the scale was individually administered with 40 persons. Each statement was read out to the respondent and in reply, the respondent stated what he/she understood from the item. If the content what the respondent comprehended and what had been conceived by the researchers matched, the item would be considered to be qualified. If mismatch

was identified, the researcher was asked, “Why did you mean the statement like this?” The response would uncover issues present in the items like vagueness, ambiguity, leading words/sentence, unfamiliar words, complicated sentence, closed ended statement, sensitive statement etc. Based on this information, statements were rephrased. The modified statements were once again read out to the respondent and feedback was received and accordingly modified. The 26 items developed after content validity testing and cognitive interviews with select respondents.

3. Results & Discussion:

All the above studies show the relationship between the Upanishadic Self-studies and with happiness, QoL self-esteem. A qualitative analysis denotes that there is a need for a relative reference frame. Hence we proposed a relative reference for the studies; Fig.1 shows 26 statements from the teachings of 11 primary upanishads from i) Taittiriyaopaniṣad : Janki Parikh (2017), ii) Kathopanishad: Swami chinmayananda (2016), iii) Chandogya: Jibananda vidyasagar(2009), iv) Mundaka: Swami Gambhirananda(2010) v) Mandukya : Swami Nikhilananda(2006), vi) Kena: Maitreya Gautam(20018), vii) Aitreya: Manindra Mishra (2017), viii) Brihadaranyaka: Charles Johnston(2016), ix). Ishopanishad: Maharishi Aurobindo (2010) x), Svethasvatara: Maheshananda Giri (1975) (xi) Prashnopaniṣad: Swami Gambhirananda (2010).

Fig.2. shows the relationship between upanishadic 26 questions and with the items from western psychology established item scales. The selected scales are 3 viz; Rosenberg Self Esteem (p. 18), 10 items, Oxford Happiness items (pp. 1073-1082), 30 items, WHO – QoL (p. 83) 27 items.

4. Scope for further study:

There is a scope for studying Vedic self-studies vs. ‘bio- energy markers. Rajesh etal (2020) has carried out a comparative study between Vedic education system & contemporary education system using ‘Bio- Energy Marker’.

5. Conclusions:

The present paper develops a conceptual reference framework

for developing a scale based on the 11 major Upanishads- from i) Taittroyopanishad, (ii) Kathopanishad (iii) Chandogyaupansishad, (iv) Mundaka, (v) Mandukya, (vi) Kena, (vii) Aitreya, (viii) Brihadaranyaka, (ix). Ishopanishad, (x) Svethasva thara, (xi) Prashnopanishad,. The process involves questionnaire development from 11 Upanishads. Item generation is done by two waynamely expert validation of the questions developed based on Upanishads. The Cron Bach alpha or internal reliability may be calculated. Exploratory and confirmatory F analysis are applied to find the inter related correlation factor. These factors may be related with the established questionnaire like Quality of Life, Self-esteem and Happiness.

Fig.1 Selected 11 major Upanishads from Indian Philosophy.

Fig. 2 Oriental and Western items for Self studies for personality development

Table 1. Oriental and Western thinking process of personality development

Table 1 gives a relative comparison between the oriental and west-

ern thinking process in personality development.

Sl. No.	Questions from vedas and Upanishads	Oxford happiness questionnaire	Quality of life scale	Rosenberg self esteem scale (RSE)
1	I get angry at small things.	I don't feel particularly pleased with the way I am.	I am happy with my present assignment.	On the Whole, I am satisfied with myself.
2	I don't have much faith in God.	I am intensely interested in other people.	My needs are satisfied.	At times I am no good at all.
3	Sitting calm is not in my interest.	I feel that life is rewarding.	My social interactions are good.	I feel that I have a number of good qualities.
4	I have no interest in Swadhyaya (study) of Ved-upanishad etc.	I have very warm feelings towards almost everyone.	I have great interest in life.	I am able to do things as well as most other people.
5	I do not hesitate in eating non-veg food.	I rarely wake up feeling rested.	I am financially independent .	I feel I don't have much to be proud of.
6	I don't know the true form of god.	I am not particularly optimistic about the future	I am happy in my Life.	I certainly feel useless at times.
7	I am not interested in the attainment of salvation.	I find most things amusing	I feel my existence is meaningful.	I feel that I'm a person of worth, at least on an equal plane with others.

Sl. No.	Questions from vedas and Upanishads	Oxford happiness questionnaire	Quality of life scale	Rosenberg self esteem scale (RSE)
8	I want to live a life containing physical pleasure.	I am always committed and involved.	What I have is enough for me.	I wish I could have more respect for myself.
9	I have no interest in enlightenment.	Life is good.	I have good relations with others.	All in all, I am inclined to feel that I am a failure.
10	My reverence is negligible in the teachings of scriptures and gurus.	I do not think that the world is a good place.	My level of aspiration is high.	I take positive attitude toward myself.
11	I do not believe in self-esteem for the acceleration of intellectual strength.	I laugh a lot.	My social prestige is high	
12	I get uncomfortable in odd circumstances.	I am well satisfied about everything in my life.	As a whole my achievement in life is high.	
13		I don't think I look attractive.	I have peace of Mind.	
14	Self study of vedas and upanishads balances life.	There is a gap between what I would like to do and what I have done.	I have time for my hobbies.	

Sl. No.	Questions from vedas and Upanishads	Oxford happiness questionnaire	Quality of life scale	Rosenberg self esteem scale (RSE)
15	I am familiar with the principle of Work.	I am very happy.	I feel secure in life.	
16	I believe that the means of liberation is knowledge.	I find beauty in some things.	I have time to know new things.	
17	I like to meditate.	I always have a cheerful effect on others.		
18	I know my 'self'	I can fit in (find time for) everything I want to.	I have been lucky in my life.	
19	I believe that God exists in every single particle.	I feel that I am not especially in control of my life.	As a Whole, I keep good health.	
20	I feel Both knowledge and karma are necessary to make life best.	I feel able to take anything on.	I feel calm and relaxed.	
21	Peace is experienced by yoga practice.	I feel fully mentally alert.	As a whole, I feel happy.	
22	I believe that God created the universe.	I often experience joy and elation.		

Sl. No.	Questions from vedas and Upanishads	Oxford happiness questionnaire	Quality of life scale	Rosenberg self esteem scale (RSE)
23	I am interested in living life sacrificingly.	I don't find it easy to make decisions.		
24	I follow the orders of my parents and teachers.	I don't have a particular sense of meaning and purpose in my life.		
25	I know the nature of the Trinity God, Jiva, Prakriti.	I feel I have a great deal of energy.		
26	I am interested in the japa of Omkaar.	I usually have a good influence on events.		
27	Human birth is meaningless without spiritual knowledge.	I don't have fun with other people.		
28		I don't feel particularly healthy.		
29		I don't have particularly happy memories of the past.		

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Sanskritresearchfoundation@gmail.com